

Correlation between Nutritional Status and Stress Response among Adolescent Girls

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Abstract:

Background: Adolescence is a critical period marked by significant physiological and psychological changes. Nutritional status during this phase plays a crucial role in overall health, influencing both physical growth and mental well-being. Recent studies have highlighted a bi-directional relationship between nutritional status and stress, with implications for adolescent health outcomes.

Aim: The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between nutritional status and stress response among adolescent girls.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Physiology in ANMMCH, Gaya, involving 300 adolescent girls aged 12-18 years. Participants were categorized based on their BMI into underweight, normal weight, overweight, and obese groups. Stress levels were assessed using a validated stress questionnaire. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing Pearson correlation and multiple regression analyses to explore the relationship between nutritional status and stress response.

Results: The study found a significant positive correlation between BMI and stress scores ($r = 0.35$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that higher BMI is associated with higher stress levels. Multiple regression analysis confirmed that BMI is a significant predictor of stress response ($\beta = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$), even after controlling for age and socioeconomic status.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that higher BMI is linked to increased stress levels among adolescent girls. This relationship highlights the need for integrated health interventions that address both nutritional status and stress management to improve adolescent health outcomes.

Recommendations: Health programs targeting adolescents should incorporate nutritional education and stress management strategies. Future research should explore the underlying mechanisms of the relationship between nutritional status and stress and develop tailored interventions to mitigate stress in overweight and obese adolescents.

Keywords: Adolescent girls, Nutritional status, Stress response, BMI, Health interventions.

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Introduction

Adolescence is a crucial time marked by profound changes in social, psychological, and physical aspects of life. During this stage, nutritional status is critical to growth and development, influencing short- and long-term health outcomes. Due to their higher nutritional needs, societal and cultural influences, and the onset of menstruation, adolescents—especially girls—face specific nutritional issues. The alarmingly high incidence of malnutrition among teenage girls worldwide, encompassing obesity and under nutrition, each with distinct health consequences, has been brought to light by recent studies.

The connection between psychological health, especially stress, and dietary status has received a

lot of attention lately. Adolescents may experience stress for a variety of reasons, including peer pressure, familial difficulties, and academic pressure. Chronic stress has been shown to have a negative impact on eating habits and nutritional status. For example, a high degree of stress has been linked to bad eating habits, such as consuming more high-fat and high-sugar foods, which can result in weight gain and obesity [1]. On the other hand, malnutrition—whether from obesity or under nutrition—can increase stress levels and set off a vicious cycle.

The reciprocal relationship between stress and nutritional status has been highlighted by recent study. According to a systematic review, eating

habits are greatly impacted by stress, and those who are under stress are more prone to experience emotional eating and binge eating behaviours [2]. Adolescent girls are especially affected by this interaction since they are more prone to eating disorders and body image issues. Research shows that higher body

Research suggests that teenagers who are overweight or obese may be more susceptible to psychological distress since a greater body mass index (BMI) is associated with higher levels of stress [3].

This relationship's physiological underpinnings include the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, which controls metabolic processes and modulates stress responses. Long-term stress that activates the HPA axis chronically can cause hormonal imbalances, including high cortisol levels, which affect appetite regulation and encourage the formation of fat. These physiological alterations may prolong stress and play a role in the development of obesity [4].

Improving teenage health outcomes requires addressing the interaction between stress and nutritional status. Promoting stress reduction strategies and a healthy diet should be the main goals of interventions. Adolescents need to learn the value of a healthy diet and appropriate coping mechanisms in order to manage stress, and this is something that schools and healthcare providers can help with greatly.

In conclusion, creating comprehensive health programs targeted at adolescent females requires an awareness of the complex link between nutritional status and stress response. Programs like these should focus on eating habits as well as mental health to lessen the negative impacts of stress and advance general development and wellness. The aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between nutritional status and stress response among adolescent girls.

Methodology

Study Design: This study will employ a cross-sectional design to investigate the relationship between nutritional status and stress response in adolescent girls.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted in the Department of Physiology at ANMMCH, Gaya over a period of 6 months.

Participants: A total of 300 adolescent girls will be recruited for this study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female adolescents aged 12-18 years.
- Currently enrolled in schools within Gaya.

- Willing to participate and provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Participants with chronic illnesses or conditions that affect nutritional status or stress levels.
- Use of medication that affects appetite or stress response.
- Pregnant or lactating adolescents.
- Those unwilling or unable to provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants will be randomly selected from various schools within Gaya. Information bias will be reduced by training data collectors thoroughly and using standardized instruments and protocols for data collection.

Data Collection: Data will be collected using structured questionnaires and physical assessments. The questionnaires will cover demographic information, dietary habits, and perceived stress levels. Physical assessments will include measurements of height, weight, and BMI.

Procedure

1. Recruitment: Participants will be recruited through schools with the help of school authorities.
2. Informed Consent: Informed consent will be obtained from participants and their guardians.
3. Questionnaire Administration: Participants will fill out standardized questionnaires on dietary habits and stress.
4. Physical Measurements: Height and weight will be measured to calculate BMI.
5. Nutritional Assessment: Nutritional status will be assessed using BMI and dietary intake data.
6. Stress Assessment: Stress levels will be measured using a validated stress questionnaire.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the data. Pearson correlation will be conducted to assess the relationship between nutritional status and stress response. Multiple regression analysis will be performed to control for potential confounding variables.

Result

Participant attributes: Three hundred teenage females in all took part in the study. Participants were 15.2 years old on average (SD = 1.8). Based on BMI classifications, the nutritional status of the subjects was distributed as follows:

A total of 300 adolescent girls participated in the study. The mean age of participants was 15.2 years (SD = 1.8). The distribution of participants'

nutritional status based on BMI categories was as follows:

- Underweight: 45 (15%)
- Normal weight: 180 (60%)
- Overweight: 45 (15%)
- Obese: 30 (10%)

Stress Levels: The stress levels of participants were categorized into three levels based on their scores from the stress questionnaire:

- Low Stress: 90 (30%)
- Moderate Stress: 150 (50%)
- High Stress: 60 (20%)

Correlation between Nutritional Status and Stress Response: Pearson correlation analysis was

conducted to assess the relationship between BMI and stress scores. The results indicated a significant positive correlation between BMI and stress scores ($r = 0.35$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher BMI is associated with higher stress levels among adolescent girls.

Multiple Regression Analysis: A multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the effect of nutritional status on stress response while controlling for potential confounding variables such as age and socioeconomic status. The regression model was significant ($F(3, 296) = 12.45$, $p < 0.001$) and explained 14% of the variance in stress response ($R^2 = 0.14$). BMI was a significant predictor of stress response ($\beta = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 1: Participant Characteristics and Stress Levels

Characteristic	N	%
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	15.2 $\pm$ 1.8	
Nutritional Status		
Underweight	45	15
Normal weight	180	60
Overweight	45	15
Obese	30	10
Stress Levels		
Low	90	30
Moderate	150	50
High	60	20

Table 2: Correlation and Regression Analysis

Analysis Type	Result
Correlation Analysis	
Pearson Correlation (BMI and Stress Scores)	$r = 0.35$, $p < 0.01$
Multiple Regression Analysis	
Predictor	B
Age	0.10
Socioeconomic Status	0.20
BMI	0.30
Model Summary	
R^2	0.14
$F(3, 296)$	12.45

Discussion

Using an average age of 15.2 years, 300 teenage girls participated in the study. 10% were obese, 15% were overweight, and 60% of the participants were of normal weight. These categories were based on the participants' nutritional health. 30% of individuals categorised their stress levels as low, 50% as moderate, and 20% as high.

Larger stress levels are linked to larger BMIs, according to a substantial positive correlation study between BMI and stress scores ($r = 0.35$, $p < 0.01$). According to this, teenage girls' stress levels tend to

rise as their nutritional condition shifts from underweight to obesity.

Subsequent research with multiple regression analysis verified that BMI is a significant predictor of stress response ($\beta = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$), while controlling for age and socioeconomic status. The regression model described 14% of the variance in stress response ($R^2 = 0.14$), and it was statistically significant ($F(3, 296) = 12.45$, $p < 0.001$). This research emphasises how BMI affects stress levels independently of age and socioeconomic position. These findings demonstrate a vital connection between teenage girls' stress reaction and

nutritional health. Adolescents who are overweight or obese tend to feel more stress than their classmates who are of a normal weight. This shows that teenagers' dietary and psychosocial needs should be met through integrated health initiatives. In order to assist reduce stress in adolescent populations that are overweight or obese, future research should investigate the mechanisms behind this link and investigate focused therapies.

Important discoveries have been made on the connection between teenage girls' nutritional health and stress response. An investigation done on teenage girls in Sidoarjo revealed a strong correlation between irregular menstrual cycles and low nutritional status as well as elevated stress levels. Their investigation revealed that two of the main causes of menstruation abnormalities in this group are poor nutrition and high levels of stress [5].

In a study published which evaluated the connection between teenage girls' body image satisfaction and their nutritional health. The results showed a significant correlation between higher degrees of body image dissatisfaction and low nutritional status. The importance of nutrition on psychological well-being was highlighted by the higher likelihood of body image worries expressed by girls with lower nutritional status [6].

Higher stress levels were associated with harmful eating patterns, according to an investigation of the dietary habits of adolescent girls under stress. Girls under severe to moderate stress were found to eat significantly less fruits and vegetables and more cereal goods, fried foods, and highly processed foods. The study emphasises stress as a potential predictor. According to this study, stress is a strong predictor of teenage females' unhealthy eating decisions [7].

Conclusion

Adolescent girls' nutritional status and stress reaction are significantly correlated, according to this study. The results show that elevated BMI is linked to elevated stress levels, with adolescents who are overweight or obese reporting higher levels of stress in comparison to their friends who

are normal weight. This association shows that BMI has an independent impact on stress even after adjusting for age and socioeconomic position. The findings highlight how crucial it is to treat teenage populations' dietary and psychological needs. To improve general well-being, health programs should include stress management techniques, especially for overweight and obese teenagers. Future studies should investigate the underlying processes of this relationship and create focused interventions to help adolescents with different nutritional statuses manage stress and achieve better health outcomes.

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